

**DETERMINATION OF FACTORS CAUSING DECREASE IN EFFICIENCY OF
REPEATED WORM FEEDING**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6942001>

Roziyeva Mohinur

PhD student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

Khaknazarova Umida

Master degree of Tashkent State Agrarian University

Ochilova Mumtozbegin

Student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

Annotation: *It is known that the growth and development of worms and the degree of formation of silk in their bodies depends on the nutritional value of mulberry leaves, that is, the amount of protein, carbohydrates, vitamins, trace elements, water and other substances in them. Based on these features, the Silk Research Institute is the only scientific center for mulberry breeding in Central Asia, and more than 70 varieties of mulberry have been created by Uzbek breeders. Currently, 9 varieties are included in the State Register. The newly created selective varieties are distinguished by their adaptability to the severe continental natural-climate conditions of our region, resistance to winter frosts, and abundant leaf production..*

Decision No. PQ-3472 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 12, 2018 "On measures to further develop the sericulture industry of the Republic" provides for the sustainable development of the cocoon industry, the establishment of special worm houses and intensive farms, and the preparation of competitive and hybrid silkworm seeds. This thesis was focused on solving the problems of correct use of the mulberry feed base and improving the technological properties of the cocoon product.

Key words: *cocooning, repetition, mulberry, silkworm, breed, hybrids, mulberry, summer season, performance, cocoon, fertility, satiety.*

In addition, in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for more effective use of the existing opportunities in the cocooning industry in the Republic" dated August 20, 2018 No. assigned to enterprises of the cocoon industry.

It is known that the growth and development of worms and the degree of formation of silk in their bodies depends on the nutritional value of

mulberry leaves, that is, the amount of protein, carbohydrates, vitamins, trace elements, water and other substances in them. Based on these features, the Silk Research Institute is the only scientific center for mulberry breeding in Central Asia, and more than 70 varieties of mulberry have been created by Uzbek breeders. Currently, 9 varieties are included in the State Register. Newly created breeding varieties are especially distinguished by their adaptation to the harsh continental natural-climate conditions of our region, resistance to winter colds, and abundant leaf production. For analysis, leaf samples were studied during spring and summer during the mid-fifth instar period. Leaf samples were taken at 8 o'clock in the morning from each cultivar during spring and repeated worm feedings. After the leaf samples were dried, the total moisture, total nitrogen, crude protein, carbonic water and crude ash content of the leaf samples were determined during the analysis.

In our research on the topic of the dissertation, we used mulberry varieties grown in the farm specializing in silk production belonging to "Agro Pilla" LLC, Beshariq district, Fergana region. In this orchard, the trees are cared for according to the same agrotechnics. Changes in the amount of nutrients in the leaves of Tajik seedless mulberry, Pioner, Kukoso-70 and Uzbek varieties, and the sensitivity of the varieties to the external environment in the summer season were studied.

The amount of nutrients in the leaves of different varieties of mulberry during the spring and summer vegetation period of the first year is given.

Therefore, it was found that in the hot weather of the summer season, a sharp decrease in water and protein in mulberry leaves, and on the contrary, an increase in ash content decreases the degree of leaf decay. The lack of moisture content in the leaves in the summer season leads to a decrease in the process of digesting food in the worm's stomach and absorbing it into the blood. Our experiment resulted in a dramatic decrease in cocoon weight, silk cocoon weight and other productivity indicators with repeated worm feeding..

Therefore, it is an extremely urgent task to maintain the number of worms in repeated worm feeding, to use productive mulberry varieties, to strengthen the processes of decay and digestion of summer leaves, and to implement them in practice.

Tall mulberry trees can be distinguished by the quantity and nutritional quality of the leaves on the branches of the head.

Since the leaves at the bottom of the branches grow earlier, they will not be the same in terms of content and nutrition. On the contrary, it was

found that the leaves in the tip part of the branch are somewhat easier to chew and digest. The effect of these characteristics of mulberry leaves on the results of repeated worm feeding in summer-autumn seasons has not been fully determined. The study of processes such as the growth and shedding of leaves on the branch was carried out in tall mulberry trees. In the first half of August, tree branches were cut diagonally in a tall tree. Then, 1/3 of the upper growth side of each branch and 2/3 of the lower side, i.e. the lower side of the head, were cut.

1/3 of the mulberry branches on three sides and 2/3 on the bottom.

(The experiment was conducted on a farm in Beshariq district, Fergana region, June 2018)

Illustration of the growth of mulberry branches on three sides and the cutting process.

The weight of three parts of branches cut from each tree and leaves taken from the lower part were determined on accurate scales. The amount of leaves in different parts of the branches was determined until 8 o'clock in the morning. The results of determining the water content of the leaves in the branches that grew during the summer vegetation show that the leaves in the upper part of the branches and the lower part of the

branches differ in this indicator to a certain extent. In particular, in the growth phase of the stem (1/3), the leaves had more water.

Taking into account that it is important to know the amount of nutrients in the leaves grown from the tips and lower parts of mulberry branches, the leaves from the tips and lower parts of the branch were chemically analyzed. As a result of the chemical analysis of the leaves on the branches, it was found that the amount of protein, total nitrogen, carbohydrates and ash in the leaves changes within certain limits.

The nutritional value of leaves from different parts of the stems can be determined by the effect on worm viability, duration of larval period and silk production. Worms were fed on the tips of mulberry branches and leaves on the lower part.

The water content of the leaves in the top 1/3 and bottom 2/3 of feeder mulberry branches

(The experiment was conducted in Beshariq district of Fergana region in June 2018)

Varieties of mulberry	Water in the leaves of three parts of the branch, %	Water in the leaves in the lower part of the stem, %	The amount of water in the leaves at the tip of the branch, %
Tajikistan seedless mulberry	71,9	66,3	8,4
Uzbekistan	70,3	65,1	8,0
Pioneer	69,5	63,9	8,7
Kukoso-70	70,0	64,2	9,0

The results of repeated worm feeding conducted during the hot summer season firstly showed that feeding on the leaves of the growing part of the mulberry head branches ensured that the genetic potential of a particular breed was not fully achieved in terms of cocoon and silk sheath weight.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED:

1. Decision PQ-2856 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2017 "On measures to organize the activities of the Uzbek Paksanoat Association". - Tashkent, 2017. p. 1-5.
2. Resolution PQ-3616 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 20, 2018 "On additional measures for the further development of the cocoon industry". - Tashkent, 2018. p. 1-4.
3. Adilov F., Kochkarov O'. Mulberry moth and its control measures. // Zooveterinary. - Tashkent, 2010. - #4. 32-p.
4. Azimjonov E.M., Jo'raev T.Kh. Infection of mulberry varieties imported from Azerbaijan under the conditions of Uzbekistan. //Scientific foundations of the development of sericulture of Uzbekistan. "Science". - Tashkent, 2001. p. 69-71..
5. Alekseychenko N.A., Babaeva G.I., Nadkernichna E.V., Bulatova Yu.O. Vliyanie microbiologicheskikh udobreniy na razvitie novykh vysokopro-duktivnykh sortov shelkovitsy. // "Scientific foundations of solving current problems in the field of silk production". "Science". - Tashkent. 2004. – S. 291-294.
6. Akhmedov N.A. The feeding period of the mulberry silkworm. //Silk. - Tashkent, 1999. - No. 1. - 22-24 p.
7. Akhmedov N.A. Ekologo-fiziologicheskie osnovy povyshenia productivity in tutovogo shelkopryada (*Bombyx mori* L.): Autoref. dis. ... d. s.x. science Tashkent: UzNIIJ, 1999. - S. 9-11.
8. Akhmedov N.A. Digestion time of mulberry leaf in silkworm body. //Silk. - Tashkent, 1999. - No. 2. - 26-28 p.
9. Akhmedov N., Bekkamov Ch., Valiev S., Jumanova U., Rahmonova Kh., Akhmedov U., Melikov B. Effect of temperature on physiological processes in the silkworm body. //Zooveterinary. - Tashkent, 2010. - No. 3. - 36 p.